

Deliverable

Project Acronym:	VRTogether
Grant Agreement number:	762111
Project Title:	<i>An end-to-end system for the production and delivery of photorealistic social immersive virtual reality experiences</i>

D4.7 - Final version of the content demonstrations

Revision: 1.0

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Delivery date: M39 (December 2020)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 762111		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: This deliverable summarizes and presents the content created for the three pilots, differentiating between geometry, textures, sounds, etc. In particular, it includes the content that has been uploaded to Zenodo, where the material is available for every user to watch, share and download.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	November 2020	Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Creation of document, first draft
0.2	November 2020	Ana Revilla Ignacio Lacosta	TheMo	First review, Second Draft
0.3	December 2020	Ana Revilla Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Second review (by Mario Montagud)
1.0	December 2020	Ana Revilla Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Final Version

Disclaimer

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This final deliverable of the Work Package 4 (WP4) group includes a summary of the final content delivered for all the pilots of the VR-Together project.

The deliverable includes a summary of the content produced within the VR-Together project in order to test and demonstrate the potential of the technology developed in the project. In order to achieve yearly milestones and to keep testing new advances in the technology, the audiovisual content was decided to be separated into three different parts or chapters with a continuous timeline.

Each pilot, produced with a specific technology, tells a part of the story, dividing the content into 3 differentiated parts: the introduction of the story (pilot 1), a continuation (pilot 2), and the outcome (pilot 3).

The content of each pilot has been uploaded to Zenodo, making the content public and available to everybody who wants to test and share it. This deliverable summarizes, with tables, the content created for every pilot, differentiating between categories: geometry of the scenario, sound, characters, textures, etc.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
AAC	Advanced Audio Coding
PCM	Pulse Code Modulation
GLTF	GL Transmission Format
VFX	Visual effects
VR	Virtual Reality
WP4	Work Package 4

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

The main purpose of this document is to present and summarize the content gathered up in previous deliverables of WP4 (D4.1, D4.3 and D4.5). Each previous document was dedicated exclusively to one pilot (1, 2 and 3, respectively). The main objective of this deliverable is:

- To summarize the content created in order to demonstrate the technology developed within the VR-Together consortium
- To summarize the content created for each pilot by different partners.
- To order the files.
- To gather up the content uploaded to Zenodo, where the users can download, share, watch and test the content that has been created for this project.

1.2. Scope of this document

This deliverable includes, exclusively, the creative content of each pilot. The scope of this document is public, with allowed access to all those outside the consortium who require it.

1.3. Status of this document

- Complete in terms of content, description and access links.
- Complete in terms of summary content tables.

1.4. Relation with other VR-Together activities

This is the final deliverable of WP4, being preceded by other deliverables that focused on each specific pilot:

- D4.1 First example of content (Pilot 1: Offline Scenario)
- D4.3 Second example of content (Pilot 2: Live Scenario)
- D4.5 Third example of content (Pilot 3: Interactive Scenario)

1.5. Deliverable content

It includes all the information regarding the content created for every pilot, detailing aspects of them, and a link to the uploaded content on Zenodo.

2. PILOT 1: OFFLINE SCENARIO

The VR episode for pilot 1 departs from the murder of a celebrity. Two users are real-time captured and tele-ported to a shared 70's look police station, where they will play the role of inspectors by attending the interrogation of two suspects.

Unlike traditional watching apart together scenarios, in which users watch exactly the same content, it was decided to place the users in a shared observation space, but in front of a different one-way mirror connecting to two separate interrogation rooms where a different suspect is being interrogated.

Therefore, although the two users share a common space and can directly see and talk to each other, they can only see and hear one of the two interrogation scenes belonging to the same story. The story includes a set of triggers to boost interaction between the users, exchanging impressions and findings to reach a conclusion about the authority of the crime.

The VR experience for pilot 1 lasts 8 minutes.

A video showcasing the pilot 1 theme and experience can be watched at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aHO5M1qNmjY>

2.1. Summary of the content delivered for Pilot 1: Offline scenario (police interrogation)

Filename	Description	Type
Room_GLTF.zip	Media Unity 3D Scene GLTF Format	.zip
Room_Unity.unitypackage	Media Unity 3D Scene Unity format	.unitypackage
User01_V1.0.jpg	Media User 1_ 360 Stereo Panorama	.jpg
User02_V1.0.jpg	Media User 2_ 360 Stereo Panorama	.jpg
User01_V1.0_mono.jpg	Media User 1_ 360 Mono Panorama	.jpg
User02_V1.0_mono.jpg	Media User 2_ 360 Mono Panorama	.jpg
Final-with-security-cam_User01__10-10- 2018.mp4	User 1_ Video billboard	.mp4
Final-with-security-cam_User02__10-10- 2018.mp4	User 2_ Video billboard	.mp4

User1_AMBI.wav	Ambisonic track_User 1	.wav
User2_AMBI.wav	Ambisonic track_User 2	.wav
User1_Mono_Audio_03-08-2018.mp4	User 1_360 Mono Video	.mp4
User2_Mono_H265_audio-17-08-2018.mp4	User 2_360 Mono Video	.mp4
SCRIPT PILOT 1.pdf	Script pilot 1	.pdf

Table 1. Summary of content delivered for Pilot 1: Offline scenario (police interrogation)

Media Unity 3D Scene GLTF Format

File name	Room_GLTF.zip
Content description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Room environment for the interrogation scene. ● Creation of the four 3D spaces for the development of the story: 2 user rooms and 2 interrogation rooms. ● Creation of all the 3D elements: table, chairs, decorative elements, etc.
Package description	Zip with geometries, textures and animations.
Purpose	3D scene for the web platform
File size	23.626 KB
Format	ZIP compressed
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1452519

Table 2. Media Unity 3D Scene GLTF Format

Media Unity 3D Scene Unity format

File name	Room_Unity.unitypackage
Content description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Room environment for the interrogation scene. ● Creation of the four 3D spaces for the development of the story: 2 user rooms and 2 interrogation rooms. ● Creation of all the 3D elements: table, chairs, decorative elements, etc.
Package description	Unity package with geometries, textures and animations
Purpose	3D scene for the web platform
File size	191.149 KB
Format	Unity package
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456486

Table 3. Media Unity 3D Scene Unity format

Media User 1_360 Stereo Panorama

File name	User01_V1.0.jpg
Content description	Panoramic picture
Package description	360 panorama image. Stereo version Point Of View from User 1.
File size	33,7 MB
Format	JPG
Dimensions	8192x8192 px
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456521

Table 4. Media User 1_360 Stereo Panorama

Media User 2 _360 Stereo Panorama

File name	User02_V1.0.jpg
Content description	Panoramic picture
Package description	360 panorama image. Stereo version Point Of View from User 2.
File size	33,7 MB
Format	JPG
Dimensions	8192x8192 px
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456521

Table 5. Media User 2 _360 Stereo Panorama

Media User 1_ 360 Mono Panorama

File name	User01_V1.0_mono.jpg
Content description	Panoramic picture
Package description	360 panorama image. Monoscopic version Point Of View from User 1.
File size	17,4 MB
Format	JPG
Dimensions	8192x4096 px
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456521

Table 6. Media User 1_ 360 Mono Panorama

Media User 2_ 360 Mono Panorama

File name	User02_V1.0_mono.jpg
Content description	Panoramic picture
Package description	360 panorama image. Monoscopic version Point Of View from User 2.
File size	17,4 MB
Format	JPG
Dimensions	8192x4096 px
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456521

Table 7. Media User 2_ 360 Mono Panorama

User 1 Video billboard

File name	Final-with-security-cam_User01__10-10- 2018.mp4
Content description	Video billboard for user 1
Package description	Video Composition in stereo of User 1. Normal audio track. Image of the composition and integration of the room in the upper side. Alpha compositing in the lower side.
File size	434 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x4096 px
Length	7'06"
Bitrate	8,000 Kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456687

Table 8. User 1_ Video billboard

User 2 Video billboard

File name	Final-with-security-cam_User02__10-10- 2018.mp4
Content description	Video billboard for user 2
Package description	Video Composition in stereo of User 2. Normal audio track. Image of the composition and integration of the room, in the upper side. Alpha compositing in the lower side.
File size	442 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x4096 px
Length	7'06"
Bitrate	8,000 Kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456785

Table 9. User 2_ Video billboard

Ambisonic track User 1

File name	User1_AMBI.wav
Content description	Ambisonic audio track for User 1
Package description	Audio track with spatial audio information
File size	233 MB
Format	WAV
Codec	PCM S24 LE
Channels	2F2R
Duration	7'05''
Bitrate	48,000 Hz
Sample rate	32
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456542

Table 10. Ambisonic track_User 1

Ambisonic track_User 2

File name	User2_AMBI.wav
Content description	Ambisonic audio track for User 2
Package description	Audio track with spatial audio information
File size	234 MB
Format	WAV
Codec	PCM S24 LE
Channels	2F2R
Duration	7:06 m
Bitrate	48,000 Hz
Sample rate	32
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456542

Table 11. Ambisonic track_User 2

User 1 360 Mono video

File name	User1_Mono_Audio_03-08-2018.mp4
Package description	Complete 360 monoscopic version for User 1. Video Composition of the full experience: Interrogation room story video and video compositing for conversation between the users. Equirectangular. Monoscopic.
File size	320 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x2048 px
Length	5'48''
Bitrate	7,000 kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1456866

Table 12. User 1_360 Mono video

User 2_360 mono video

File name	User2_Mono_H265_audio-17-08-2018.mp4
Content description	Complete 360 monoscopic version for User 2. Video Composition of the full experience: Interrogation room story video and video compositing for conversation between the users. Equirectangular. Monoscopic.
Package description	Video Composition in equirectangular, mono with the full experience for User 2
File size	778 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x2048 px
Length	6'55"
Bitrate	15,000 kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/1457163

Table 13. User 2_360 Mono video

User 1 360 stereo video

File name	User1_Stereo_Audio_03-08-2018.mp4
Content description	Complete 360 stereoscopic version for User 1. Video Composition of the full experience: Interrogation room story video and video compositing for conversation between the users. Equirectangular. Stereoscopic.
Package description	Video Composition in equirectangular, stereo with the full experience for User 1
File size	652 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x2048 px
Length	5'48''
Bitrate	15,000 kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4384650

Table 14. User 1_360 Stereo video

User 2_360 stereo video

File name	User2_stereo_H265_audio_17-08-2018.mp4
Content description	Complete 360 stereoscopic version for User 2. Video Composition of the full experience: Interrogation room story video and video compositing for conversation between the users. Equirectangular. Stereoscopic.
Package description	Video Composition in equirectangular, stereo with the full experience for User 2
File size	777 MB
Format	MP4
Codec	MPEG AAC Audio
Dimensions	4096x2048 px
Length	6'55"
Bitrate	15,000 kbps
Frame rate	29,97 fps
Audio	48,000 Hz
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4384652

Table 15. User 2_360 Stereo video

3D Character Models and Animation Data for pilot 1

File name	VRT_Pilot1_Character_Animations.zip
Content description	This dataset contains the 3D Animated Characters as used for the Pilot 1 experience of the VR-Together project. The animated characters come as a set of FBX files with associated diffuse and normal maps.
Format of files	.fbx, .png
Size	160.8 MB
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3662390

Table 16. 3D Character Models and Animation Data for pilot 1

Script of pilot 1

File name	SCRIPT PILOT 1.pdf
Content description	Script with the dialogues and interactions between characters from pilot 1. See Annex I.
File size	113.2 kB
Format	PDF
Pages	14
Thumbnail	<p style="text-align: center;">VR TOGETHER EPISODE 1 THE ARMOVA CASE</p> <p>USER 1 - THE INTERROGATION OF RYAN ZELLER</p> <p>FADE IN:</p> <p>INT. INTERROGATION ROOM - LATE NIGHT</p> <p>The user is sitting on the dark side of an interrogation room, looking at a one-way mirror. Through the mirror they can see the lighted side of the room, a spartan concrete box featuring just a bare table and two simple chairs.</p> <p>In the user's side of the room, resting on a table in front of the user and a bit to his side, a screen is playing a recording on loop - a CCTV recording showing the entrance to Armova's apartment, with a timestamp: "17.45" We see ZELLER arriving at the door, and going in. The CCTV recording jumps ahead - timestamp "18.19". We see ZELLER going out and walking away. Another cut - "19.25". CHRISTINE arrives, wearing a spaghetti strap dress, her shoulders exposed and pale, no bandage on her arm. The recording jumps ahead - timestamp "22.03". CHRISTINE exits the building hurriedly, clutching her left arm, and runs away. The recording keeps looping.</p> <p>Enter the SARGE, a middle-aged British cop, a tad jaded, slumped shoulders betraying his tiredness. He closes the door, drops a heavy folder on the table, then approaches the mirror and stares at the user, voice edged with sarcasm.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">SARGE Well, here we are. Back with the cool kids. Let's make this good, inspector.</p> <p>He sits on the table and skim-reads through the dossier.</p>
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4384129 (See Annex I)

Table 17. Script of the first pilot

3. PILOT 2: LIVE SCENARIO

Pilot 2 continues the murder investigation story developed in pilot 1. In this second episode, the users are tele-ported to a TV set where a news show is about to start. The host, who is live captured, broadcasted and integrated from a remote Chroma key room, shares with the audience the latest news about the murder. Up to four users are integrated in real-time inside the TV set, not only acting as the audience but also being able to interact with the presenter.

The interactions also influence the pace at which related content and connection with experts are being presented. At some point, a special live connection with an anchor, located near the crime scene, is made to know more details about the crime and ongoing investigations. The connection through realistic and panoramic video gives the feeling of being transferred to that location, increasing the feeling of presence.

The VR experience for pilot 2 lasts 6 minutes.

A video showcasing the pilot theme and experience can be watched at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KfpTlyS5cAO>

3.1. Summary of content delivered for Pilot 2: Live Scenario

Filename	Description	Type
Presenter_With_Audio.mp4	Video of the presenter with green background	.mp4
Stereoscopic video in front of the crime scene	Reporter_With_Audio.MOV	.mov
Stereoscopic video of Howard	Howard_With_Audio.mp4	.mp4
TVSet.unitypackage	Geometry set package	.unitypackage
SCRIPT PILOT 2	Script of the second pilot	.pdf

Table 18. Summary of content delivered for pilot 2: Live Scenario

Video of the presenter with green background

File name	Presenter_With_Audio.mp4
Content description	Video of the presenter in stereo format and green background for real-time background removal.
Codec	H264-MPEG-4 AVC
Resolution	1040x600
Framerate	29.97 fps
Bitrate	13,500 kbps
Audio	48,000 KHz
File size	541.3 MB
Format	MP4
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3264940

Table 19. Video of the presenter with green background

Stereoscopic video in front of the crime scene

File name	Reporter_With_Audio.MOV
Content description	Video of the reporter in stereo format 180°.
Codec	H264-MPEG-4 AVC
Resolution	5760x2880
Framerate	29.97 fps
Bitrate	8805 Kbps
Audio	48,000 KHz
File size	159 MB
Format	.MOV
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3264970

Table 20. Stereoscopic video in front of the crime scene

Stereoscopic video of Howard

File name	Howard_With_Audio.mp4
Content description	Video of the news anchor in stereo format.
Codec	H264 - MPEG-4 AVC
Resolution	1536x768
Framerate	30 fps
Bitrate	3579 kbps
Audio	48,000 KHz
File size	28 MB
Format	MP4
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3265029

Table 21. Stereoscopic video of Howard

Geometry set package

File name	TVSet.unitypackage
Content description	Unity package containing the TV set scene where all the pilot 2 happens.
Package description	Unity package containing all the geometry in FBX format, audio in MP3 format, animations and placeholders for the user, presenter, commentator and outdoor action.
Purpose	Unity scene to allocate all the assets
File size	16.8 Mb
Format	.unitypackage
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3265039

Table 22. Geometry set package

Script from pilot 2

File name	SCRIPT PILOT 2.pdf
Content description	Script with the dialogues and interactions between characters from pilot 2. See Annex II.
File size	113.2 kB
Format	PDF
Pages	14
Thumbnail	<p style="text-align: center;">INT. TV STUDIO - DAY</p> <p style="text-align: center;">OFFICER SCRIPT</p> <p>Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FARE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">GAVIN</p> <p>Welcome back, ladies and gents, to this special edition of "Hearaay". I'm Gavin Michaels. Shocking news out of London today as we learned of the death of hotel maven and society darling, Elena Amova. Did you all hear about this?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">USERS (AND FARE USERS)</p> <p>Yes... terrible... couldn't believe it... (etc.)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">GAVIN</p> <p>Police are being very tight-lipped about this case, refusing to comment on cause of death or even if they suspect foul play. What do you think?</p>
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4384150 (see Annex II)

Table 23. Script of the second pilot

4. PILOT 3: INTERACTIVE SCENARIO

Pilot 3 brings the third and last episode of the murder investigation story. This third chapter takes place in the victim’s apartment where the police team together with up to five real-time captured users work as a team to find clues and come up with a conclusion about what happened to the victim and the authority of the crime.

This new experience adds new layers of interaction, enabling the users to interact with the environment, by touching objects, and to talk to the characters. It also allows navigating between dependences of the apartment, thus supporting 6DoF. These new features are supposed to increase the user’s engagement, who becomes a protagonist of the plot and not just a spectator, while still feeling together with other users in the shared environment.

The VR experience for pilot 3 lasts approximately 10 minutes.

4.1. Summary of content delivered for Pilot 3: Interactive Scenario

Filename	Description	Type
Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage	Geometry of living room, textures and illumination.	.unitypackage
Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage	Geometry of kitchen, textures and illumination.	.unitypackage
Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage	Geometry of bedroom, textures and illumination.	.unitypackage
Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage	Objects, textures and illumination.	.unitypackage
VRTogether_III_Scene1_v.2_LO.mov	Video Composition (Scene 1)	.mov
VRTogether_III_Scene2_v.1.mov	Video Composition (Scene 2)	.mov
VRTogether_III_Scene3_v.1.mov	Video Composition (Scene 3)	.mov
VRTogether_III_Scene4_v.1.mov	Video Composition (Scene 4)	.mov
Pilot 3 - Sound.zip	Sound and SFX	.zip
Pilot3-Characters-And-Animation.zip	3D Character Models and Animation Data	.zip

SCRIPT PILOT 3.pdf	Script of the second pilot	.pdf
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Table 24. Summary of content delivered for pilot 3: Interactive Scenario

Geometry, textures and illumination of the living room

File name	Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage
Content description	This dataset contains the material created for the living room of the pilot 3. It includes a full 3D hyper realistic environment where scenes 1 and 4 take place in. It contains the following material: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Geometry of the living room● Textures of objects and the environment● Illumination scheme
Size	905.5 MB
Format	.unitypackage
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288514

Table 25. Geometry, textures and illumination of the living room

Geometry, textures and illumination of the bedroom

File name	Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage
Content description	This dataset contains the material created for the bedroom of the pilot 3. It includes a full 3D hyper realistic environment where scene 2 takes place in. It contains the following material: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Geometry of the bedroom● Textures of objects and the environment● Illumination scheme
Size	905.5 MB
Format	.unitypackage
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288514

Table 26. Geometry, textures and illumination of the bedroom

Geometry, textures and illumination of the kitchen

File name	Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage
Content description	<p>This dataset contains the material created for the kitchen of the pilot 3. It includes a full 3D hyper realistic environment where scene 3 takes place in. It contains the following material:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Geometry of the kitchen● Textures of objects and the environment● Illumination scheme
Size	905.5 MB
Format	.unitypackage
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288514

Table 27. Geometry, textures and illumination of the kitchen

Materials, textures and illumination of objects

File name	Pilot3_GeometryMaterialsTextures.unitypackage																											
Content description	<p>This dataset contains the objects created for all the scenes of the pilot 3. It includes objects from scenes 1 to 4. In particular, it includes the 3D creation files of the following objects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Glass ● Forensic brush ● Evidence bag ● Phone inside bag ● Frame ● SD card ● Notebook ● Pen ● Phone finder ● Futuristic device ● Forensic camera ● Futuristic laptop 																											
Size	905.5 MB																											
Format	.unitypackage																											
Thumbnails	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>	Phone finder	Futuristic device	Forensic camera	Futuristic laptop																							
Glass	Forensic brush	Evidence bag	Phone inside bag																									
Frame	SD Card	Notebook	Pen																									
Phone finder	Futuristic device	Forensic camera	Futuristic laptop																									
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288514																											

Table 28. Materials, textures and illumination of objects

Video Composition (Scene 1)

File name	VRTogether_III_Scene1_v.2_LO.mov
Content description	Video composition of the first scene of the Pilot 3 of the VR-Together project.
Resolution	3840x2160
Codec	Timecode, Linear PCM, H.264
Duration	4'51''
Audio	Stereo
Size	892.2 MB
Format	.mov
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288607

Table 29. Video Composition (Scene 1)

Video Composition (Scene 2)

File name	VRTogether_III_Scene2_v.1.mov
Content description	Video composition of the second scene of the Pilot 3 of the VR-Together
Resolution	3840x2160
Codec	Timecode, Linear PCM, H.264
Duration	1'52''
Audio	Stereo
Size	327.3 MB
Format	.mov
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288621

Table 30. Video Composition (Scene 2)

Video Composition (Scene 3)

File name	VRTogether_III_Scene3_v.1.mov
Content description	Video composition of the third scene of the Pilot 3 of the VR-Together
Resolution	3840x2160
Codec	Timecode, Linear PCM, H.264
Duration	1'49''
Audio	Stereo
Size	62.3 MB
Format	.mov
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288629

Table 31. Video Composition (Scene 3)

Video Composition (Scene 4)

File name	VRTogether_III_Scene4_v.1.mov
Content description	Video composition of the fourth and last scene of the Pilot 3 of the VR-Together project
Resolution	3840x2160
Codec	Timecode, Linear PCM, H.264
Duration	1'20''
Audio	Stereo
Size	224.3 MB
Format	.mov
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288635

Table 32. Video Composition (Scene 4)

Sound files

File name	Pilot 3 - Sound.zip
Content description	Sound files for the Pilot 3 of the VR-Together project. It includes individual dialogues for each character (Sarge, Elena, Rachel and Evans) in each scene (from 1 to 4) and the special effects.
Number of files	23
Format of files	.wav
Audio	44,1 kHz
Size	224.3 MB
Format	.zip
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288753

Table 33. Sound files

3D Character Models and Animation Data

File name	Pilot3-Characters-And-Animation.zip
Content description	This dataset contains the 3D characters and animations as used in Pilot 3 of the VR-Together project. It contains the 4 characters of the associated experience and their post-processed motion capture animation data in the FBX format, as well as the texture data in the PNG format.
Format of files	.fbx, .png
Size	1.2 GB
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4288286

Table 34. 3D Character Models and Animation Data

Script from pilot 3

File name	SCRIPT PILOT 3.pdf
Content description	Script with the dialogues and interactions between characters from pilot 3. See Annex III
File size	172.3 kB
Format	PDF
Pages	22
Thumbnail	<p><u>ORIGINAL VERSION OF THE SCRIPT</u></p> <p>INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY</p> <p>Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armova. At the table in the middle of the room find SARGE, cataloguing evidence bags. Various TECHS crisscross the room now and then, searching for delivering evidence.</p> <p>Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.</p> <p>SARGE Ah... here we go.</p> <p>He sets his notebook down and stands.</p> <p>SARGE (CONT'D) For the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. Not only do I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a childminder? Well, don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?</p> <p>Sarge points to User One.</p> <p>SARGE (CONT'D) As long as you're here, make yourself useful and hit that light switch. It's a bit dark in here.</p> <p>User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change to a calming blue, and soothing, meditative music begins to play.</p> <p>SARGE (CONT'D) What the hell...? Turn it off, turn it off.</p> <p>User One complies.</p> <p>SARGE (CONT'D)</p>
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/4384168 (See Annex III)

Table 35. Script of the second pilot

5. CONCLUSIONS

The objectives and the summary of the three-year project are:

1. Creation of a story that allows an appropriate demonstration of the potential of the technology developed. This technology development includes the achievement of real-time elements, scalability goals (up to 5 users) and multi-source contents.
2. The creation of high quality content following the same story during the three pilots, achieving the following goals:
 - a. To record between 6 and 7 minutes of content for each pilot about a police investigation.
 - b. To use an avant-garde technology that allows us to visualize ourselves in real time while we watch the story and see others users enjoying the experience at the same time.
 - c. To create content and 3D environments of hyper-realistic quality.

ANNEXES

ANNEX I. Pilot 1: Offline Scenario

VR TOGETHER EPISODE 1

THE ARMOVA CASE

USER 1 - THE INTERROGATION OF RYAN ZELLER

FADE IN:

INT. INTERROGATION ROOM - LATE NIGHT

The user is sitting on the dark side of an interrogation room, looking at a one-way mirror. Through the mirror they can see the lighted side of the room, a spartan concrete box featuring just a bare table and two simple chairs.

In the user's side of the room, resting on a table in front of the user and a bit to his side, a screen is playing a recording on loop - a CCTV recording showing the entrance to Armova's apartment, with a timestamp: "17.45" We see ZELLER arriving at the door, and going in. The CCTV recording jumps ahead - timestamp "18.19". We see ZELLER going out and walking away. Another cut - "19.25". CHRISTINE arrives, wearing a spaghetti strap dress, her shoulders exposed and pale, no bandage on her arm. The recording jumps ahead - timestamp "22.03". CHRISTINE exits the building hurriedly, clutching her left arm, and runs away. The recording keeps looping.

Enter the SARGE, a middle-aged British cop, a tad jaded, slumped shoulders betraying his tiredness. He closes the door, drops a heavy folder on the table, then approaches the mirror and stares at the user, voice edged with sarcasm.

SARGE

Well, here we are. Back with the cool kids. Let's make this good, inspector.

He sits on the table and skim-reads through the dossier.

SARGE

What do we have here? Miss Yelena Armova, age 27...

(holds a picture for a second)

Rather easy on the eyes. Owner of an hotel empire, found dead in her Mayfair residence.

(looks up, winks at the mirror)

The tabloids must be all over this, eh? Guess that explains why the big shots at Europol got us out of bed in the dead of night. Alright, let's see it through.

(reads from the dossier)

Next witness, RYAN Zeller, age 34, playboy with a reputation for nastiness, saw Armova before she died.

(raises his voice)

Alright, let's get started!

A few seconds later, ZELLER enters the room, all confidence and swagger. An aging dilettante who hasn't accepted he's not

in his twenties any more. His natural insolence and flamboyance are boosted with some substance - he moves erratically and occasionally slurs his words. He stands there for a second, looking around the room.

ZELLER

Whoa. This is the real deal, huh?

SARGE

Mister Zeller, take a seat. Tell us about last night, and especially... mister Zeller?

ZELLER ignores the policeman and heads to the mirror, seemingly fascinated, almost tripping on the chairs.

ZELLER grins and shields his eyes to see through the glass.

ZELLER

Hellooo. Hello? Someone there?
Someone home? You bet...

With a sigh, SARGE approaches, taps ZELLER on the shoulder.

SARGE

Mr. Zeller!!!

ZELLER turns around nonplussed, as if he saw SARGE for the first time - then loses balance.

ZELLER

Not guilty. I didn't kill him, I mean her. Just here for the show.

SARGE

Sir, Have you taken drugs?

ZELLER

(running out of steam)
Drugs? Ha! You call them drugs, I call... it... breakfast.

ZELLER tries to straighten his back and stand but his knees falter. SARGE catches him before he falls, then shoots the user a resigned look through the mirror before helping ZELLER into one of the chairs.

ZELLER

(mumbling)
Oh man, this is a shithole.

SARGE sighs, obviously tired with the whole scene.

SARGE

Not your kind of suite, eh, Zeller?

ZELLER

Well, it's... not the Ritz.

SARGE slams a hand on the table and leans towards him, intimidating. He's had enough.

SARGE

But it's a bloody good warm-up for the jail. You can talk, or you can start getting used to it.

ZELLER claps, laughing, then coughs. He gestures with a trembling hand, pointing at SARGE, the mirror and the door.

ZELLER

Bravo. Hard cop. I've seen this one. You're gonna talk tough to me for a while, and then a nicer guy steps in, maybe a woman, she's all smooth, so I spill. You gonna rough me up too?

(leans forwards, pointing to his own face, hopeful)

Hit me a couple times maybe, for the bragging rights? Nah?

(he sits back, disappointed, gestures around)

I guess all you have is this shit job, right?

SARGE

Alright, here's what I don't get, Zeller. You are filthy rich. You could have avoided this. You waived your rights because you wanted to

talk to us. So talk. Why did you kill her?

ZELLER

Oh, I didn't.

SARGE

You're famous for having a temper.

ZELLER

uhm

SARGE

It doesn't make you look good. You're going to be famous as a murderer. A crime of passion.

ZELLER throws his arms up and shouts festively:

ZELLER

Bravo! Case closed! Well done, Sherlock!

SARGE remains silent, surprised with the confession...

ZELLER

(suddenly serious)

A crime of passion. You got that right. But, alas, I didn't do it. She did.

SARGE

So you're saying it's a suicide?

That sends ZELLER into a fit of laughter.

ZELLER
Not her. HER.

ZELLER points to, in the direction of the other room. SARGE looks towards the user. Right there, the LIGHTS GO OUT for a second, then they come back.

SARGE
(deadpan)
Who were you talking about?

ZELLER
Oh, come on. I know you have that glorified secretary in the can as well. Always hovering around her like,
(mimicking CHRISTINE)
"Lena sign this, Lena let me handle that, Lena you're late, Lena don't do drugs, Lena don't breathe." Fucking hell. Lena knew she wasn't working just for her.

SARGE
Miss Gérard?

ZELLER
Yeah, whatever. The menial.

SARGE
What do you mean, miss Gérard wasn't working only for Lena?

ZELLER

You think she can afford that with the pittance Lena paid? Selling her secrets. I told Lena, she wouldn't listen. Maybe she told her too, pillow talk or something.

SARGE

Industrial espionage, eh?

ZELLER

I'm doing your job here, officer.

SARGE

So if miss Gérard was selling Armova's secrets, who was buying? If we're talking business competitors, then right now I'm looking at a strong suspect. Wasn't she kicking you out of all major western European resorts?

For the first time, ZELLER visibly tenses up. He sits a bit straighter, pauses. Suddenly serious and calculating.

ZELLER

(quietly angry)

That has nothing to do with this.

SARGE

You have motive, opportunity, you're sitting there trying to find a scapegoat. I could sell it.

ZELLER

(interrupting)

You could try.

SARGE

(unfazed)

...or you could tell me what you actually know, if you really believe it was miss Gérard.

ZELLER

(gesturing to the other room)
Well, talk to her! Ask her about her real job, spying on Lena for years...

The outburst makes ZELLER a little dizzy. He blinks, shakes his head to clear it. SARGE tut-tuts.

SARGE

Easy on the booze, Zeller.

ZELLER

I'm fine... a bit under the weather.
Just need to stretch my legs...

ZELLER gets up, carefully, closely watched by the cop.

SARGE

What time did you get to her apartment?

ZELLER walks up to the mirror again. He blinks uneasily.

ZELLER

Eh, six? Maybe five-thirty...

...And then Chris arrived...

...made a fuss...

...We had a drink...

...At eight or so.

SARGE

(nodding at the user)

OK, we'll check.

(back at ZELLER)

We found blood on the crime scene,
Zeller, but it wasn't Lena's. Did
someone get hurt?

ZELLER

Blood? No...

ZELLER gasps for air, eyes wide open.

ZELLER

I didn't... do... do-don't...

SARGE

(impatiently)

I need facts, Zeller! When you left,
was miss Gérard still with miss...

ZELLER retches and drops to the floor, spasming. SARGE jumps
to his feet and tries in vain to wake ZELLER up.

SARGE

What the... Medic! We need a medic!

FADE OUT:

USER 2 - THE INTERROGATION OF CHRISTINE

FADE IN:

INT. INTERROGATION ROOM - NIGHT

The user is sitting on the dark side of an interrogation room, looking at a one-way mirror. Through it they can see the lighted side of the room, a spartan concrete box containing just a table and two chairs.

In the user's side there's an open dossier, resting on the table. It reads: "Forensic analysis of the body: (under way), Preliminary cause of death: widespread trauma stemming from fall from balcony. Forensic analysis of the room has focused on three glasses of whisky, one of them containing chemicals (symptoms: dizziness, euphoria, disorientation, vomit, heart failure if untreated)."

In the lighted side of the room, SARGE is reading a dossier.

SARGE

(he looks up at the user)

Have you read the dossier, inspector?

(he reads)

Yelena Armova, age 27, top
businesswoman, darling of the London
tabloids, found dead in her Mayfair
mansion. No witnesses, no leads.

(winks at the user)

Sounds like we're out on a wing and
prayer, eh? So let's close this case
soon. I'd rather be having a pint in

Margate, instead of a friendly chat with...

(he reads again)

Miss CHRISTINE Gérard, age 30, Armova's assistant. Last person to see her alive.

(yelling)

Send her in, lads!

A few seconds later, CHRISTINE enters the room and stops.

CHRISTINE is a professional-looking woman, composed and conservatively made-up. Her movements and gestures are tightly controlled, as she's trying to rein in her emotions. She's wearing trousers and a short-sleeved shirt, all very office-smart. A big adhesive bandage covers most of her left forearm.

She stands at the threshold for a second, looking at the cop, the table and the mirror.

SARGE

Come in, CHRISTINE. I hope you have some answers for me...

CHRISTINE

(coldly)

I don't think we're on a first-name basis yet. Sir.

SARGE does a mock bow, indicating the chair.

SARGE

Touché, ma'am. If you would be so kind as to take a seat, ma'am.

CHRISTINE sits, reluctantly. SARGE turns to the mirror.

SARGE

Where were you last night? Exact times.

CHRISTINE

I had been reviewing Le... miss Armova's schedule with her, at her apartment.

(Sarge looks at her)

She had to attend a cocktail at the embassy, so we wrapped up and I left.

Must have been nine o'clock.

SARGE

And what time did you arrive?

CHRISTINE

(without hesitation)

Twenty-five past seven.

SARGE turns around to look at her.

SARGE

That's surprisingly precise
timekeeping, miss Gérard.

CHRISTINE

I suppose I am a surprisingly precise
individual, officer. That's why I am
Le... was, miss Armova's assistant.

SARGE

Was she a generous employer?

CHRISTINE

(choosing her words)
She was... correct. Stern, but fair.

SARGE

By which you mean she was stingy as
hell and notoriously vicious. You
seem pretty well-off, miss Gérard.
Your account shows quite a tidy sum,
for a secretary.

CHRISTINE

With all due respect, you didn't know
miss Armova, officer. I did. She was
a great businesswoman, a mentor, and
an inspiration. And may I add, my
finances are none of your business.

SARGE

(without missing a beat)
Did you hurt yourself?

CHRISTINE

(taken by surprise)
Beg your pardon?

SARGE

Your wrist.

CHRISTINE touches the bandage on her arm, reflexively.

CHRISTINE

Oh, no... well, in a way. I fell down some stairs last week. I hope that's not a crime yet, inspector?

SARGE

Devil's in the details, miss Gérard. So you arrived at miss Armova's apartment at 7.25 and departed at 9. We'll check.

(he nods to the user)

Were you two alone during all that time?

CHRISTINE

(with evident distaste)

No. A... friend of miss Armova was there as well.

SARGE

Who?

CHRISTINE

RYAN Zeller. They had a... private conversation, and then he left.

SARGE

What time?

CHRISTINE

I don't recall.

SARGE

That's a surprise. I thought you were a very exact woman.

CHRISTINE

I was miss Armova's assistant, not Zeller's. She was supposed to attend a charity fundraiser in Milan today. We went over the details and then I left.

The lights flicker and go out for a second, then they're back. SARGE walks around the table, her gaze following him.

SARGE

Miss Gérard, would you describe yourself as a loyal employee?

CHRISTINE

Of course!

SARGE is now standing next to CHRISTINE, so that she needs to look up to face him. CHRISTINE frowns, uncomfortable.

SARGE

You strike me as an exceptionally devoted employee, you do. Much more than anyone would reasonably expect,

considering miss Armova's reputation
for cruelty and ruthlessness.

CHRISTINE

(irritably)

And what are you implying, officer?

SARGE

You knew Lena very well, didn't you?
Perhaps better than anyone else. How
long have you been her assistant?

CHRISTINE

Three years. But she's miss Armova...

SARGE

(implacably)

Three years. Traveling with her,
living with her. Must have been quite
a bonding experience, Lena and you.

CHRISTINE

(raising her voice, exasperated)

I don't like your tone, officer...

SARGE

(talking over her)

Such an impressive devotion. I can
absolutely understand why you didn't
want Zeller around her.

CHRISTINE

Zeller wanted her dead...

SARGE

(louder)

And how would you know that?
Obviously you had a mission, but you
grew too attached to her during those
years...

CHRISTINE

(furious)

I won't stand here and...!

SARGE

(drones on, talking over her)

It was more than your job. It was
your life. You wanted to keep her to
yourself, keep Lena away from men
like Zeller...

CHRISTINE gets up, fists clenched.

CHRISTINE

She is Miss Armova to you!

SARGE

...you were jealous. All those years,
all your loyalty, and Lena couldn't
be faithful to you, she had to get
high with Zeller, she never valued
what you sacrificed to be with her...

CHRISTINE

(yelling, lost all composure)

She's miss Armova to you! Don't you
bloody call her Lena, you pig! You

don't know her! Zeller wanted her gone, and I told her! But she didn't listen, so I followed her to the kitchen... confused..., she got angry, Zeller was... she grabbed...

CHRISTINE shuts up abruptly, sits down, trembling, nursing her arm. SARGE follows her movement, squatting to keep eye level.

CHRISTINE

(suddenly calm and cold)
He did it. Zeller. He's your man. I was only trying to protect her from him.

SARGE

And what did you do to protect her?

CHRISTINE

I warned her. I tried to keep him away. She thought he loved her, but it was just business to him..

SARGE

And what was it to you? I think you were working for Zeller, and now that the going gets tough you're turning on him. Did Zeller tell you to poison her?

CHRISTINE looks at him. Suddenly, she smiles, a mirthless, savage smile. All her shyness is gone. She's in control.

CHRISTINE

What!! Nice try. He's using me to cover his ass. Are you sure it was her that was poisoned?

SARGE
(realising he's made a mistake)
Come on, CHRISTINE

CHRISTINE
I want a lawyer.

CHRISTINE
(interrupting)
I. Want. A. Fucking. Lawyer.

CHRISTINE crosses her arms, eyes defiant. SARGE looks back at her for a couple of seconds, then at the user.

SARGE
I'll be.. Alright, we're done here.

CHRISTINE gets up, and before walking out, she shoots a victorious smile at the user.

ANNEX II. Pilot 2: Live Scenario

INT. TV STUDIO - DAY

OFFICER SCRIPT

Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FAKE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at

the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.

GAVIN

Welcome back, ladies and gents, to this special edition of "Hearsay". I'm Gavin Michaels. Shocking news out of London today as we learned of the death of hotel maven and society darling, Elena Armova. Did you all hear about this?

USERS (AND FAKE USERS)

Yes... terrible... couldn't believe it... (etc.)

GAVIN

Police are being very tight-lipped about this case, refusing to comment on cause of death or even if they suspect foul play. What do you think?

He turns to FAKE USER 1-

FAKE USER 1

Yeah... it would be pretty unusual for someone so young and healthy to just drop dead like that.

Gavin turns to FAKE USER 2 (in spot 3)-

GAVIN

Do you agree?

FAKE USER 2

Foul play, for sure.

GAVIN

What are your most pressing questions about this case?

FAKE USER 3

How much money did Zeller stand lose because of Armova?

GAVIN

Good question... speaks to motive. Any more?

FAKE USER 2

Why did Christine Gerard, the assistant, lie about her wrist wound? She's gotta be guilty of something.

GAVIN

We'll see if we can get any more info out of the police. ...So have you all heard about this new technology that interrogators can use? They take security footage, news recordings, personal videos... everything a person has ever recorded... and then they feed it into an artificial intelligence program that can then recreate someone's personality? Let's talk to Howard Chapman.

HOWARD

It's pretty cutting edge. This would allow police to actually

interview the victim herself. It would be fascinating to see if they're planning to use the technology in this case...

GAVIN

...Thank you Howard. And now to answer all our burning questions, we have our correspondent on the scene in Mayfair, Maria Espinoza...

Gavin turns and the screen behind him switches to the street in front of Armova's apartment building, where MARIA stands holding a microphone.

MARIA

That's right, Gavin. I'm Maria Espinoza, reporter here. Police have been in and out of Miss Armova's building all day...

GAVIN

Maria, our audience wants to know what's happening with suspects Ryan Zeller and Christine Gerard. They both seem to have something to hide.

MARIA

Yes, despite the police silence around this case, rumors are flying. Ah, it looks like someone is coming out now, yes...

She moves toward the police tape by the front door, where SARGE (from Video 1) is exiting the building.

As she does so, the audience is immediately transported to the street in front of Armova's apartment, now watching the scene as if they are right there.

MARIA (CONT'D)

I'm going to see if I can speak
with the officer who's just come
out...

Raising her hand and shouting-

MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Officer stops with an annoyed huff, but appears willing to
be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

OFFICER

Officer Pearson, Metropolitan
Police Service.

MARIA

Officer, what can you tell us
about the death of Elena Armova?
Was this murder?

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on an
ongoing investigation. You'll have
to wait for the press briefing like
everyone else...

MARIA

But Officer, our viewers have
questions...

(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Officer, do you think Ryan Zeller
killed Armova?

The Officer pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on
anything or anyone related to this
case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Officer turns and walks toward his car as Maria follows,
doggedly.

OFFICER

I'm sorry, no comment.

MARIA

...What about Christine Gerard,
Miss Armova's assistant?

Officer stops for a moment.

MARIA (CONT'D)

Miss Gerard visited the victim the
night of the murder and has an
unexplained injury, what can you
tell us about that?

Officer turns, an accusatory eye for the persistent reporter.

OFFICER

Where did you get your information?

MARIA

Miss Gerard is rarely far from Miss Armova's side. Her absence from the public eye over the last twenty-four hours is suspect, to say the least. Wouldn't you agree?

OFFICER

I am unable to comment at this time.

MARIA

Will the police be employing their controversial new AI technology in this case? Will you be interviewing Armova herself?

Officer turns back toward her, thoughtful for a moment.

OFFICER

Since Miss Armova was such a public figure, that is an option.

(MORE)

OFFICER (CONT'D)

I'm afraid I can't say any more than that. Now if you'll excuse me...

Officer tips his hat and exits the scene. Maria turns back to the camera with a shrug.

MARIA

There you have it, Gavin. Police are refusing to comment on the two individuals with the closest ties to Armova. However, Officer Pearson did confirm that AI technology may be used to help solve this crime.

Our world once again becomes the TV studio, with Maria and the street scene on a screen behind the hosts.

GAVIN

Very interesting, Maria, thank you.

He turns back to the Users.

GAVIN (CONT'D)

Well, audience, was it the boyfriend, Zeller? The assistant, Gerard? Was it suicide? A botched robbery? A drug overdose? What do you think?

FAKE USER 2

It would be nice to get in that apartment and have a look around.

GAVIN

Yes, and I bet you'd love to hear from Armova herself, wouldn't you? That might answer a few questions. Well, ladies and gents, that's our

program for today. Be sure to tune in next time to see me and for more on this story, and all the news you just can't stop talking about, on the next edition of... "Hearsay".
I'm Gavin Michaels...

Closing titles swirl, music fades as the studio goes dark.

THE END

INT. TV STUDIO - DAY

SERGEANT SCRIPT

Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FAKE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.

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to this special edition of
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Shocking news out of London today
as we learned of the death of
hotel maven and society darling,
Elena Armova. Did you all hear
about this?

USERS (AND FAKE USERS)

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couldn't believe it... (etc.)

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Why did Christine Gerard, the assistant, lie about her wrist wound? She's gotta be guilty of something.

GAVIN

We'll see if we can get any more info out of the police. ...So have you all heard about this new technology that interrogators can use? They take security footage, news recordings, personal videos... everything a person has ever

recorded... and then they feed it into an artificial intelligence program that can then recreate someone's personality? Let's talk to Howard Champman.

HOWARD

It's pretty cutting edge. This would allow police to actually interview the victim herself. It would be fascinating to see if they're planning to use the technology in this case...

GAVIN

...Thank you Howard. And now to answer all our burning questions, we have our correspondent on the scene in Mayfair, Maria Espinoza...

Gavin turns and the screen behind him switches to the street in front of Armova's apartment building, where MARIA stands holding a microphone.

MARIA

That's right, Gavin. I'm Maria Espinoza, reporter here. Police have been in and out of Miss Armova's building all day...

GAVIN

Maria, our audience wants to know what's happening with suspects Ryan Zeller and Christine Gerard. They both seem to have something to hide.

MARIA

Yes, despite the police silence around this case, rumors are flying. Ah, it looks like someone is coming out now, yes...

She moves toward the police tape by the front door, where SARGE (from Video 1) is exiting the building.

As she does so, the audience is immediately transported to the street in front of Armova's apartment, now watching the scene as if they are right there.

MARIA (CONT'D)

I'm going to see if I can speak with the officer who's just come out...

Raising her hand and shouting-

MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Sarge stops with an annoyed huff, but appears willing to be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

SARGE

Sergeant Hoffstetler, Metropolitan Police Service.

MARIA

Sergeant, what can you tell us about the death of Elena Armova? Was this murder?

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment on an ongoing investigation. You'll have to wait for the press briefing like everyone else...

MARIA

But Sergeant, our viewers have questions...

(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Sergeant, do you think Ryan Zeller killed Armova?

The Sarge pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment on anything or anyone related to this case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Sarge turns and walks toward his car as Maria follows, doggedly.

SARGE

I'm sorry, no comment.

MARIA

...What about Christine Gerard, Miss Armova's assistant?

Sarge stops for a moment.

MARIA (CONT'D)

Miss Gerard visited the victim the night of the murder and has an unexplained injury, what can you tell us about that?

Sarge turns, an accusatory eye for the persistent reporter.

SARGE

Where did you get your information?

MARIA

Miss Gerard is rarely far from Miss Armova's side. Her absence from the public eye over the last twenty-four hours is suspect, to say the least. Wouldn't you agree?

SARGE

I am unable to comment at this time.

MARIA

Will the police be employing their controversial new AI technology in this case? Will you be interviewing Armova herself?

Sarge turns back toward her, thoughtful for a moment.

SARGE

Since Miss Armova was such a public figure, that is an option.

(MORE)

SARGE (CONT'D)

I'm afraid I can't say any more than that. Now if you'll excuse me...

Sarge tips his hat and exits the scene. Maria turns back to the camera with a shrug.

MARIA

There you have it, Gavin. Police are refusing to comment on the two individuals with the closest ties to Armova. However, Sergeant

Huffstetler did confirm that AI technology may be used to help solve this crime.

Our world once again becomes the TV studio, with Maria and the street scene on a screen behind the hosts.

GAVIN

Very interesting, Maria, thank you.

He turns back to the Users.

GAVIN (CONT'D)

Well, audience, was it the boyfriend, Zeller? The assistant, Gerard? Was it suicide? A botched robbery? A drug overdose? What do you think?

FAKE USER 2

It would be nice to get in that apartment and have a look around.

GAVIN

Yes, and I bet you'd love to hear from Armova herself, wouldn't you? That might answer a few questions. Well, ladies and gents, that's our program for today. Be sure to tune in next time to see me and for more on this story, and all the news you just can't stop talking about, on the next edition of... "Hearsay".

I'm Gavin Michaels...

Closing titles swirl, music fades as the studio goes dark.

THE END

ANNEX III. Pilot 3: Interactive Scenario

ORIGINAL VERSION OF THE SCRIPT

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armoval. At the table in the middle of the room find SARGE, cataloguing evidence bags. Various TECHS crisscross the room now and then, searching for delivering evidence.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

For the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. Not only do I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a childminder? Well, don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

As long as you're here, make yourself useful and hit that light switch. It's a bit dark in here.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall.

When they press it, the lights in the room change to a

calming blue, and soothing, meditative music begins to play.

SARGE (CONT'D)
What the hell...? Turn it off, turn
it off.

User One complies.

SARGE (CONT'D)

It's all controlled by computer or
something... we haven't been able
to gain access. Rich people, eh?
Always finding new ways to throw
their money away.

Turning to User Two.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Well, how about you put new
batteries in that torch there.

Next to User Two is a table with a flashlight, battery
compartment open, and a large battery. User Two can pick up
the battery with one hand and the light with the other, and
insert the battery into the compartment. Screwing the cap on
turns on the beam.

SARGE (CONT'D)
There now. That's better.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a
bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking
device.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, Rachel, there you are.

(turning to the Users)

This is our Technology Officer, Rachel Long. She's going to set up this new AI system that's got everyone in a frenzy. Rachel... the Civilian Oversight Committee I was telling you about.

RACHEL

Yes... hello.

She nervously lays the device on the table and begins setting it up.

SARGE

Seems like a lot of nonsense, but they say since she was such a public figure, there's enough data to make it work. If you ask me, it's good old-fashioned detective work that will solve this case.

Rachel finishes her final adjustments and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other. Sarge flashes his badge.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been robbed? I have a very sophisticated security system. You control it with that remote you have there... along with everything else in the apartment.

Sarge slides the remote across the table toward User Three.

SARGE

Oh good, maybe the light switch is on there.

ELENA

Just hold down button three for a few seconds, that will reset everything in the room to the default settings.

User Three does so, and the lights come up to normal.

SARGE

Ten million Euros to tell us how to turn the lights on. That's quite the investment.

Rachel stiffens, eager to show off what the technology can really do.

RACHEL

Miss Armova, we were wondering what you could tell us about last night. Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and more agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting with my board of directors... I was supposed to meet Christine later... Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant. I should call her, she'll be worried...

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it. Any idea where you might have left it?

ELENA

I usually set it on the charger when I come home... just over there by the entrance.

The charger is clearly empty.

ELENA (CONT'D)

But I have a phone finder in that drawer there.

She points to a table behind User 4.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make the phone alarm. It's a separate unit from the phone, so it works even if the phone's off.

User 4 opens the drawer, removes the remote and presses the button. One of the evidence bags on the table begins to make a really annoying noise. Sarge picks up the bag, and we see a small round button shaped device inside. Sarge presses it, and the noise stops.

SARGE

So that's what that is. Found it in the trash earlier. Seems someone doesn't want us to find your phone, Miss Armova. Can you think of any reason why that might be?

ELENA

No... I don't know...

SARGE

Do you believe that either Miss Gerard or your boyfriend, Mr. Zeller, would have any reason to wish you harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I

was planning on ending things with Ryan. I do expect him to be quite upset when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA

No... if you must know. I was involved with someone else. Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE

Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA

None of your business, Officer.

SARGE

A crime's been committed here, "Miss Armova". I'll need to interview this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel, annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Can't you do something?

RACHEL

Like what?

SARGE

Make her answer.

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Look, Miss... whatever you are.
We're trying to solve a murder
here.

ELENA

A murder? Whose?

SARGE

Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions--

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA

Mine? That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE

No, a hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing here
talking to me, and I don't have
time for the coy games. Tell me who
the other fella was, or I'm turning
you off.

RACHEL

Actually... the procedure for
shutting her down--

SARGE

It. The thing is a machine, Rachel.

RACHEL

Right, but it's a very complex
machine, so...

Rachel's voice trails off as she notices that Elena's

hologram has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker here as she gets further away from the projection device?). She quickly picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...
She follows Elena into an adjoining room. Sarge turns to the group, specifically to address User 5.

SARGE
Well well... how about you. Do you think we'll get an answer out of her about her new beau? Yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 5
Yes.

SARGE
Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 5
No.

SARGE
Me neither. Waste of time, most likely.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Either way, I'm headed into the kitchen to do some real police work. Follow me or go with Rachel

and her little toy, up to you.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women. The Users decide which group to follow.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is examining two wine glasses by the sink.

SARGE

Two different shades you say?
That's interesting. What are the chances she changed lipsticks in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS who have decided to join him.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, good. Now you'll get to see some real crime-solving. Evans here was just telling me that there are two different shades of lipstick on these wine glasses. Having a drink with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three different sets of fingerprints, actually.

SARGE

Three? Now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, then pulls out the card and puts it on the table.

EVANS

If you could stick that in my laptop there and hit enter, the program is all set up. It'll do the rest.

User 1 goes to the table and inserts the card, presses Enter.

The computer screen flashes to an image that says

"processing" and some kind of progress bar.

SARGE

Let me guess... Armova, Gerard and Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2:

Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Sometimes it doesn't take a rocket scientist. So which sample came from which glass?

Evans turns the laptop and starts pecking at keys.

EVANS

Interesting thing... One glass had all three fingerprints. The other, just Gerard.

SARGE

So either one of them could have put something in her drink.

(thinks a moment, turns to the Users)

Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in my assumptions back there with that... device?

(to User 2)

Tell me, yes or no: do you think Armova's new love interest... was Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2

Yes.

SARGE

Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2

No.

SARGE

You sure? Something Zeller said when we brought him in... about pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Fair to say there were enough
secrets among the three of 'em to
fill a teenage girl's diary.

RACHEL (O.S.)
Sarge? Evans? We found something!

Sarge and Evans look at each other, curious.

SARGE
Let's have a look then.
Sarge leads the group out.

Evans picks up his laptop and tags
along behind.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL) -

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users enter to find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed,
staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her,
Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

Rachel looks up from the device.

RACHEL
Ah, good. I've got her settled down
a bit. I think she'll be more
responsive now.
(turning to Armova)
Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who
the new person in your life was...
is? We'd really like to talk to
them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

At least you didn't assume, like
that old dinosaur in there.

Her eyes wander back to the picture.

ARMOVA (CONT'D)

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are
arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at
first. What Zeller couldn't get out
of me with pillow talk, he paid
Gerard to supply. But his plan
backfired. Christine and I fell in
love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did
you ever suspect she was doublecrossing
you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA
No! Christine would never betray me
like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL
Do you think she suspects more than
she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1
Yes.

RACHEL
Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1
No.

RACHEL
Something about her body language
tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Miss Armova... what were you
celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA

A major deal with a Greek resort chain. Christine had only been working for me for a few months. She was still on Ryan's payroll, but the sparks were flying. Late nights, traveling together... our first kiss was a few weeks after this picture was taken. But...

She becomes emotional.

RACHEL

What is it, Miss Armova? You can tell us. It's very important that you're completely honest with us.

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA

Everything you need to know is on the SD card hidden in that picture frame.

Rachel looks to User 2, nodding toward the picture frame-

RACHEL

Go ahead... see what you can find.

User 2 picks up the picture frame, pulls the back off, and finds an SD card taped to the back of the picture.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Sergeant Hoffstetler will want to see that right away.

Rachel and the Users head back toward the Living Room.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

Rachel's group enters the space first, following Rachel.

RACHEL
Sarge? Evans? We found something!
She turns to the User who has the picture frame.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Go ahead and set that on the table.

The other group enters, led by Sarge. Rachel indicates the frame now lying on the table.

Sarge pulls the SD card off the frame and hands it to Evans, who sits down and puts it into his laptop.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
(to Sarge)
Did you find anything interesting in the kitchen?

SARGE
You bet. Fingerprints on the wine glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both had the opportunity to introduce the poison into Armova's glass. Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL
Gerard... so that could be motive.

EVANS
And so could this.

All attention in the room focuses on Evans as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)
Seems Armova had someone hack into Gerard's bank accounts... she was receiving payments from Zeller every few weeks... up until just last Monday.

RACHEL
She never stopped working for Zeller. If Armova found out... Gerard might have good reason for wanting to keep her quiet.

SARGE
Sounds like we have motive, means and opportunity, ladies and gentlemen. Time to bring in Miss Gerard... in handcuffs this time.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy piece of technology is worth something after all.
(to the Users)
And thanks for your help. You're welcome back any time, as far as I'm concerned. Good work, everyone. Someone hit that light switch again, eh?

He stretches out on the sofa and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)
I think I've earned a bit of a kip.

A User hits the switch on the wall, and the lights fade down to the dim blue they were before, and then all the way to black.

THE END

ADAPTED SCRIPT DUE TO COVID-19

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armova. At a table in the middle of the room find SARGE.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Just for the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a nanny? Don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

While you're here, make yourself useful, it's a bit dark in here. Hit that light switch, would you?

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, turn it on.

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, on the wall,
behind you, turn on the lights!

(When they do:)

SARGE (CONT'D)
There we go, that's better.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking device.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Ah, Rachel.
(turning to the Users) Everybody,
This is Rachel Tyrell, she's our
Tech Officer. Rachel, this is the Civilian
Oversight Committee I was telling you
about. Rachel is going to install the
AI system that's got everyone in a
frenzy.

RACHEL
Yes... hello.

SARGE
Seems like a lot of nonsense, but
they say since she was such a public
figure, there's enough data to make
it work.

Rachel lays the device down on the table, looks at it and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been robbed? I have a very sophisticated security system.

Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and more agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting with my board of directors... I was supposed to meet Christine later... Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant. I should call her, she'll be worried...

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it.
Any idea where you might have left
it?

ELENA

I have a phone finder.

She points to a table behind User Four.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make
the phone ring.

SARGE

Go on, then.

Presumably User Four presses the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Go on, press the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Press the button on the remote
that's on the cabinet, go on!

(Once they do:) One of the evidence bags on the table begins to
make a really annoying noise.

SARGE

So that's what that is.

SARGE

Look, Ms. Armova, do you have any
reasons to suspect why Christine
Gerard or your boyfriend, Ryan
Zeller, may wish you to do harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I was planning on ending things with Ryan. I do expect him to be quite upset when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA

No... if you must know. I was involved with someone else.

Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE

Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA

None of your business, Officer.

SARGE

Look, "Miss", I'm trying to solve a crime here. I need to get to know this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel, annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Can't you do anything with her?

RACHEL

Like what?

SARGE

Like make her answer!

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Look, Miss... whatever you are.
We're trying to solve a murder
here.

ELENA
A murder? Whose?

SARGE
Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions—

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA
That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE
No, you're not. A hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing right here
talking to me, and I don't have time
for the coy games. So if you don't tell me who
the other boyfriend is, I'll turn you
off!

Rachel notices that Elena's hologram
has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker here as she
gets further away from the projection device?). She quickly
picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...

She picks up her machine and follows Elena into an adjoining

room. Sarge turns to the group, addressing User Five.

SARGE
Well well... you, listen out.
Do you think we'll
get more information about her
new beau out of her?

--option 1--

USER 1
Yes.

SARGE
Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 1
No.

SARGE
Me neither. Waste of time, if
you ask me.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Either way, I'm headed into the
kitchen to do some real police
work. Two groups, two of you
with me, and two of you with Rachel
and her new toy.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is
examining three glasses by the sink.

SARGE
Two shades?

That's interesting. What are the chances Armova changed her lipstick in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, there you are. Now you'll get to see some real police work. Young Evans here was just telling me that there are two different shades of lipstick on the glasses. So what, Armova was having a drink with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three different sets of fingerprints, actually.

SARGE

Three? Uh, now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, and the information appears.

SARGE

Don't tell me... Armova, Gerard and Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2: Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)

You see, sometimes you don't have
to be a rocket scientist.
So which sample came
from which glass?

EVANS

Gerard, Zeller and Armova.

The results pop up.

SARGE

So either one of them had a
good opportunity to put
some poison in her drink.
(thinks a moment, turns to
the Users)
Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in
my assumptions back there with
that... device?
(to User 2)
Tell me, yes or no: do you think
Armova's new love interest... was
Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2

Yes.

SARGE

Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2

No.

SARGE

You sure? Something Zeller said
when we brought him in... about

pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)

Fair to say there were enough secrets between the three of 'em to fill a teenage girl's diary.

(beat)

But it's not enough to get a conviction, not yet. I do hope Rachel's group has something. You two stay, I'm gonna see what she found.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL)-

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed, staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her, Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

RACHEL

Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who the new person in your life was... is? We'd really like to talk to them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at first. What Zeller couldn't get out of me with pillow talk, he paid Gerard to supply. But his plan backfired. Christine and I fell in love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did you ever suspect she was doublecrossing you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA

No! Christine would never betray me like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL

Do you think she suspects more than she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1

Yes.

RACHEL

Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1

No.

RACHEL

Something about her body language tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Miss Armova... what were you celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA

A major deal with a Greek resort chain. Christine had only been working for me for a few months. She was still on Ryan's payroll, but the sparks were flying. Late nights, traveling together... our first kiss was a few weeks after this picture was taken. But...

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA

Everything you need to know is on the SD card hidden in that picture frame.

Rachel looks to User Two, nodding toward the picture frame. Rachel takes it.

Rachel picks up the back of the picture frame (the part that has the SD card taped to it) and heads for the door.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

I'll see if Sarge has finished in the kitchen. Wait here for a moment.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

The groups arrive in the Living Room together to find Sarge, Rachel waiting for them.

RACHEL
Sarge, we found something here, and you?

She pulls the SD card into his laptop.

SARGE
You bet. Fingerprints on the glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both had the opportunity to put poison her. Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL
Gerard... so that could be motive.

All attention in the room focuses on Sarge as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)
Seems Armova had someone hack into Gerard's bank accounts... she was receiving payments from Zeller every few weeks... right up until last Monday.

RACHEL
She never stopped working for Zeller. If Armova found out... Gerard she had a good reason to keep her quiet.

SARGE
Looks like we have, means, motive and opportunity, ladies and gentlemen. I think it's time to bring in Miss Gerard, once again. This time, in handcuffs.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy
toy of yours is worth
something after all.

(to the Users)
And thanks to all of you. You're
welcome back any time, as far as I'm
concerned. Good job, everyone.

He stretches out and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)
I think I've earned a bit of a rest.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Go on then, don't make me change
my mind back again.

(Assuming they do:) A User hits the switch on the wall, and
the lights fade down to the dim blue they were before, and
then all the way to black.

THE END